

QUIZ**LAST NAME: BARRANCO FABRE****FIRST NAME: ADRIAN****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes).

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author used the following software: MSOffice ProPlus

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

- Turabian's Handbook specifies that the arrangement of entries on the bibliography is mostly done by alphabetical order by author. In the case there are more works written, edited or translated by the same person, how should the bibliography be organized.**
 - Alphabetically by title.¹**
 - Following the usage order.
 - Chronologically.
 - It will not matter the order, but the sources must be there.
- On Europe the decimal point is expressed as comma, but for Turabian style is specified to use period. While citing and European source, how should the number 9 400,36 be written inside a quotation?**

¹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, ed. Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, and Joseph M. Williams, 8th edition, Chicago Guides to Writing, Editing, and Publishing (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 93.

‘... 9 400,36 ...’.²

‘... 9 400’36 ...’.

‘... 9 400.36 ...’.

‘... 9 400 ...’.

3. **Some year ago, authors still used Latin terms or abbreviations for shortening the citations on notes. Nowadays, Turabian allows the use of only one of them. Which is it and what does it mean?**

Idem, meaning ‘the same’.

Ibid, meaning ‘in the same place’.³

Op. cit., meaning ‘in the works cited’.

Loc. Cit., meaning ‘in the place cited’.

4. **Turabian manual emphasize the use of ‘competing views to improve’ our research. What does that mean?**

That the researchers must search deeply until they find sources that agrees with them.

It means that researchers should compete between them to see who is right.

To search and understand the sources that disagrees with your hypothesis and point of view.⁴

It means that all the sources that we found are valuable even the ones that do not relate to our subject.

² Turabian, 191.

³ Turabian, 99.

⁴ Turabian, 25.

5. **Countries that want to be part of European Unions must fulfil certain criteria to apply. Which is one of the most important?**
- Change his currency to Euro.
 - Be part of United Nations.
 - Accept the existence of Kosovo.
 - Accept the entire acquis (body of EU law) and translate it to their national language.⁵**
6. **On European Union official documents, what is the correct way to write surnames?**
- Sentence case (first letter uppercase and the rest lowercase).⁶**
 - All uppercased.
 - All lowercased.
 - It depends on the person.
7. **Knowing that Post-positivism in a research implies to correlate and compare experimental date. It would be qualitative or quantitative?**
- Quantitative.⁷**
 - Qualitative.
 - Both.
 - Neither of them.

⁵ European Commission, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, 7th edition (European Commission, 2011), 51.

⁶ European Commission, 44.

⁷ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: Sage Publications, 2008), 8.

8. **What would be the best method to collect demographic data as gender and ethnicity of the participants for a research?**
- Interviews.
 - Focus group.
 - Online research.
 - Survey.**⁸
9. **Turabian suggest the author to rigorously identify words and ideas from other sources while taking notes, and to prevent confusing them with our own. If a writer rephrases what other author wrote and does not give credit to the author, he is committing...**
- Paraphrasing.
 - An anonymous quotation.
 - Plagiarism.**⁹
 - An ethical behaviour.
10. **The common plan to follow on a report or thesis as specified on Turabian Handbook, and if the professor or university does not stablish another one, is the following:**
- Introduction – Theoretical Framework – Discussion - Conclusion.
 - Introduction – Methods and Materials – Results – Discussion - Conclusion.**¹⁰

⁸ Bloomberg and Volpe, 72.

⁹ Turabian, 33.

¹⁰ Turabian, 43.

- Introduction – Theoretical Framework – Methodology - Conclusion.
- Introduction – Methodology - Conclusion.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End*. Los Angeles: Sage Publications, 2008.
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